

Action Plan Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment CoARA

2026-2029

Preamble

The University of Orléans has been a signatory of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) since 2025. This action plan reflects a commitment to responsible, open and inclusive research and is part of a broader European and international approach to transform research assessment practices, both at the individual and institutional levels. The University of Orléans is already engaged in a process of continuous improvement of its practices through the HR Excellence in Research Award (HRS4R) label, which it obtained in 2020.

This document presents the University of Orléans' action plan for the coming years. In order to represent the research community as a whole, a working group was established, primarily composed of researchers from all fields, as well as research support staff. Several meetings were organised to introduce the initiative and, during dedicated workshops, to develop the various actions that make up this plan.

A number of evolutions in research assessment practices had already been introduced, particularly through discussions within the Academic Council. Through this plan, the University of Orléans now commits more formally to this transformation.

The steering committee that coordinated this work will oversee the implementation of the action plan at the University of Orléans and will remain informed of developments at both national and international levels. The working group composed of teacher-researchers and research support staff that produced this document will meet annually to review the University's progress and reassess its position with regard to these commitments.

Our Positioning on the Various Commitments

1. Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research

The University of Orléans will continue its efforts to better recognize the diversity of research activities carried out by researchers¹. In this regard, it commits to:

- Differentiating the specific characteristics and practices of each discipline. To do so, the University will rely on the information provided by the sections of the National Council of Universities (CNU) and may ask the chairs of the Disciplinary Expert Committees (CED) to provide a jointly drafted guide outlining the specific features of each section.
- Taking into account the full scope and nature of activities in research, teaching, administration, and collective responsibilities. The nature and scope of these activities will need to be specified in order to assess the level of engagement beyond purely quantitative indicators. For instance, particular attention will be given to teaching methods rather than simply the number of hours taught. Similarly, the involvement in doctoral supervision should be considered without being limited to quantitative aspects alone. The supervision work carried out by non-accredited teacher-researchers will also have to be recognized by encouraging doctoral schools to record it systematically in ADUM.

¹ Throughout this document, the term "researcher" is used as a generic term that includes doctoral students, postdoctoral researchers, teacher-researchers, and researchers from National Research Organisations (NRO).

- Including other research outputs: software, datasets, books, patents, etc. in the assessment of research valorisation, in the same way as publications.
- Highlighting practices such as investment in reproducibility, the development of research–action–training plans (for instance, in the context of participatory research), Science with and for Society (SwafS), and Open Science (OS).
- Assessing fairly across the various types of research (fundamental research, experimental research, innovation, etc.).
- Encouraging risk-taking, and ambitious projects, for instance by valuing scientific work that represents a genuine breakthrough compared to existing knowledge.
- Taking into account thematic and/or geographic mobility, as well as, where applicable, career interruptions or periods outside academia.
- Encouraging the description of the nature of research activities (role and level of involvement in projects, impact of the project on the community, creation of collaborative networks) and research administration tasks (collective activities, involvement within the laboratory), rather than listing positions or projects.
- Taking into account research and teaching environments (university laboratories, French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS), French National Institute of Health and Medical Research (INSERM), etc.), as well as specific constraints (for example: research sites located far from teaching locations within the University, researchers working at regional campuses, confidentiality of research topics).
- Recognizing activities related to grant applications and responses to calls for proposals, even when unsuccessful. These activities are often unavoidable in the absence of baseline research funding and given the prevalence of project-based funding, yet they are highly time-consuming. The scientific contributions arising from these applications (new research themes, new collaborations, developing an international network or new internal dynamics) may be explicitly acknowledged despite the lack of funding.

2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators

For research assessment, the University of Orléans aims to rely more on qualitative indicators.

To this end, it plans on:

- Co-constructing the assessment criteria with the evaluators (members of the Academic Council, Disciplinary Expert Committees, laboratory directors, and heads of academic divisions) and communicating them transparently to those being assessed.
- Ensuring compliance with the guidelines and framework established for the preparation of the application file during the assessment process. The evaluator will rely solely on the information provided in the file, which must be readily verifiable.
- Requesting a detailed presentation of five significant publications or outputs in CVs. Applicants will be asked to explain their innovative nature and specify their individual contribution, in order to help non-specialist reviewers form an informed opinion without necessarily understanding the full content.

- Relying on the opinions of the National Council of Universities (CNU) when they provide differentiating assessments.
- Taking into account the specific conditions under which research activities are conducted (e.g.: researchers who are geographically or thematically isolated, career interruptions).
- Raising awareness among researchers of questionable publication practices (predatory reviews, salami slicing, etc.).
- Not considering the language of publication as an evaluation criterion in disciplines where it is justified.

3. Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication- based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index

The University of Orléans intends to continue reducing the use of quantitative indicators in research assessment.

In particular, the h-index is not considered an appropriate indicator for assessment, as it is highly dependent on fields and research communities. The University of Orléans therefore aims to take it out of assessment practices.

Similarly, the Journal Impact Factor (JIF) is not necessarily a reliable indicator of the reviews' quality level. However, to help non-specialist evaluators, the University of Orléans may rely on review or conference ratings established within each field, where such classifications exist.

4. Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

International rankings of research organisations can be interpreted and used in different ways. The University of Orléans distinguishes two main purposes.

- The first deals with visibility and communication. Appearing in such rankings can help small and medium-sized universities improve their visibility at regional, national, and international levels. This may for instance facilitate the development of new collaborations and access to additional funding. Aware of the lack of transparency in the methodologies used by some rankings, the University of Orléans intends to initiate a reflection on its participation in such rankings.
- The second deals with the use of these rankings for assessing laboratories and research. Given the lack of clarity regarding their calculation methods, the University of Orléans opposes the use of these indicators for research assessment. It will not use these rankings to (i) assess laboratories, (ii) make funding allocation decisions, or (iii) assess collaborative projects.

5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to

The University of Orléans will implement training initiatives and communication measures related to this action plan for research assessment.

It will also work towards recognizing and valuing research assessment activities.

6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes

There is no action planned under this item.

7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use

The University of Orléans will carry out communication actions within the research community regarding the reform of research assessment. Doctoral students, postdoctoral researchers, and master's students will also be targeted through awareness-raising activities.

It will also ensure transparent communication on evaluation criteria. In particular, internal guidelines already define these criteria for promotions and the allocation of bonuses and are disseminated to all staff members. They will also be regularly reviewed.

8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition

The University of Orléans will engage in exchanges at the national level with the French chapter of CoARA. Many research units operate under multiple supervisory institutions (such as the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS), the University of Tours, or INSA Centre Val de Loire): coordination with these partners will be essential to harmonize research assessment practices.

9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments

The University of Orléans will publish its action plan on its website and on Zenodo, and will implement institutional communication actions to disseminate information to the University's research community. The CoARA work group will meet at least once a year to review and progress on the content of this action plan.

10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research

There is no action planned under this item.

